

THE ISSUE OF MODERN EDUCATION AND INDEPENDENT WORK IN PRIMARY GRADES.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7698508>

Abstract: In this article, the issue of innovative reforms in the primary education system and modern organization of independent work is analyzed scientifically and theoretically.

Key words: developmental education, primary education, innovative technologies, integration in education, independent education, basic principle, system, etc.

The issue of improving the education system and applying innovative technologies has become one of the main tasks of our state that must be solved in education. Today, a number of activities are being carried out in the education system, starting with general education schools, in the development of the field of education. The impact of the modern education system on students is extremely important. The weight of personnel with intellectual potential is of high importance in determining its socio-economic development and future of every country.

One of the main principles in the development of the primary education system is the reform of the structure and content of education. For this, our main task is to train highly qualified and competitive specialists, to harmonize the activities of educational personnel, to introduce educational innovations and advanced pedagogical technologies into the educational process. One step forward in education cannot be made without first changing the teacher's work in primary education. Because the student is first given basic knowledge by his first teacher. When innovative technologies are used in primary education, the teacher's skills and the learner's independent work skills are formed. Multimedia and video lessons are the most widely used innovative technologies in primary education. . The use of multimedia technologies in the educational system leads to the development of personal individual characteristics, activity in the educational process, creative approach to each subject, and information processing competencies. Based on this issue, the goal and objectives of the research are to develop educational integrations and innovative lesson plans, to create theories of innovative approaches to education. Wide implementation of recommendations and suggestions aimed at improving the possibilities of teaching in the use of developmental education in the educational process; - in the test program development and practical application of test lesson plans for students of elementary education and sports educational work of planned pedagogic higher educational institutions; The five important initiatives put forward by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on March 19, 2019 show that the role and importance of the educational institution in educating socially active students and youth is very high. Because, in this proposed "Five most important initiatives, it is necessary to further strengthen the attention to the youth, to involve them in culture, art, physical education and sports, to form the skills of using information technologies in the youth, to encourage reading among the youth of our country. promoting, ensuring women's employment" is important for the development of socially active citizenship competences for

the future of the country, for mature, young people to grow up as a mature generation. A specific aspect of the stage of development of modern higher pedagogical education is a purposeful, substantive and technological change in the training of future teachers. The change of the goal-setting apparatus is conditioned by the acceptance of the student as the subject of his educational activity, that is, the change of the paradigm of the relationship between the teacher and the student in the process of the subject-object relationship to the subject-subject (personal) relationship; substantive and technological changes should ensure the achievement of new goals. The problem of professional training of a teacher is of particular importance today in the country where the political and economic changes are rapidly changing, that is, the social and cultural role is assigned to the teacher. Implementation of developmental education and preparation of educational activities of elementary school students is promoted as the most important component of this system. Determining the essence of preparing the future teacher for the implementation of developmental education for elementary school students, clarifying its uniqueness, structure and functions, analyzing the legal relations between the components of this system, laying the foundation for its implementation implies the determination of principles and result-target directions. It is necessary to understand the essence of the preparation of the future teacher for the implementation of the educational development of primary school students and to imagine it as a whole system in order to implement a number of activities. In order to determine the effectiveness of the use of developmental education in training, it would be appropriate to conduct experiments and tests in several ways. 60110500 - Elementary education and sports educational work is planned to be taught in the VII semester of the educational direction). In these processes, the following main criteria were observed: No subjective effects on the calculation results during the experiment-testing process The description of the parameters of the researched process was correctly recorded without omitting 1. In order to objectively determine the effectiveness of the research results, the experimental test results were regularly analyzed and selected according to statistical criteria. determining the effectiveness of the complex aimed at increasing the effectiveness of teaching in the use of education, conducting regular questionnaires and surveys among future primary education teachers, monitoring students' acquisition of theoretical knowledge and performance of practical tasks , conducting tests and handouts and evaluations in control and test groups, etc is to determine changes in students' cognitive activity based on the mathematical and statistical analysis of the results.

Extracurricular reading and recitation lessons are introduced to children's fiction in 20 minutes of lessons once a week in the 1st grade. The goal is to instill in young children a love for books and independent reading. Basically, the students of this class are taught skills and abilities such as how to deal with books, the rules of reading books, how to preserve books, how to observe the behavior of the heroes of the work, how to study the positive aspects, how to retell stories in a figurative way. For the students of this class, mostly books with pictures are taken. By reading books that develop children's emotions, the teacher introduces them to our independent country, its beautiful cities, villages, national traditions, values, past, and people's dreams. They have a passion for knowledge.

In the 2nd grade, students read small works independently based on the teacher's help and assignment. In this class, an extracurricular reading lesson is held once every 2 weeks. The

teacher finds and selects works about the courage of the motherland and ancestors, plants, birds and animals and recommends them to the students for reading.

In the 3rd-4th grades, artistic and popular scientific works are recommended for independent reading of students in extracurricular activities, which vividly describe people's lives and reflect their spiritual and moral lifestyle. In 3rd-4th grades, extracurricular reading lessons are held once every two weeks. In these classes, the teacher continues to collect age-appropriate books in the classroom library. The study corner outside the classroom can be decorated in different ways. In this, the teacher and the student work together. Artistic and popular scientific works serve to expand and form the worldview of students only if they are read independently and consistently. Reading outside the classroom instills love for goodness and hatred of evil in children, develops connection, speech, literary - serves to raise aesthetic thinking.

First of all, children's literature gives joy to children with its interesting content, the beauty of artistic images, the expressiveness of the language, the musicality of poetic words. At the same time, it also has an educational effect on children. tells stories from children's lives, children's games, early childhood, and dreams. In this regard, fairy tales are of great importance.

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